

4 pairs of 4-component spinors for $SL(4,C)$, their transformation properties and $SL(4,C)SL(4,C)^*=SO(3,1)$ connection

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Abstract: In certain basis, $SL(3,1)$ can be written as a matrix direct product of $SL(2,C)$ and $SL(2,C)^*$. One direct consequence of this relation is that $SO(3,1)$ can also be conceived as a commutative matrix product of $SL(4,C)$ and $SL(4,C)^*$. For example, in polarization optics, any non-singular, non-depolarizing Mueller matrix, M , that belongs to the proper orthochronous Lorentz group is equal to the commutative product of a 4×4 complex matrix Z and its complex conjugate, $M=ZZ^*=Z^*Z$, where Z is an element of $SL(4,C)$ and it is the 4×4 analogue of the 2×2 Jones matrix of $SL(2,C)$.

In this note we define 4×4 versions of the Pauli matrices and their 4-component generalized contravariant eigenvectors. We show that these eigenvectors transform as right-chiral spinors and their covariant counterparts transform as left-chiral spinors under $SL(4,C)$ and outer product of their pairwise combinations can be associated with the 4-vector of the Minkowski space.

0.1 Introduction

Let L be an element of $SL(2,C)$ in an exponential form with parameters θ and η :

$$L = \exp\left(-\frac{i}{2}(\vec{\theta} \cdot \vec{\sigma} + i\vec{\eta} \cdot \vec{\sigma})\right) \quad (1)$$

$\vec{\sigma}$ is the Pauli vector with $\sigma_1 = \sigma_x$, $\sigma_2 = \sigma_y$, $\sigma_3 = \sigma_z$. We rewrite L and its complex conjugate in the following compact forms:

$$L = \exp\left(-\frac{i}{2}\vec{\pi} \cdot \vec{\sigma}\right), \quad L^* = \exp\left(\frac{i}{2}\vec{\pi}^* \cdot \vec{\sigma}^*\right) \quad (2)$$

$\pi_i = \theta_i + i\eta_i$ and $*$ denotes complex conjugation.

In this note L can be the proper orthochronous Lorentz transformation that acts on left-chiral spinors with θ_i and η_i being rotation and boost parameters, or L can be the non-singular Jones matrix¹ of polarization optics that transforms the Jones vector of completely polarized light, and θ_i and η_i now being the birefringence and dichroism parameters, respectively.

In polarization optics, it is well known that 4×4 version of the Jones matrix can be obtained as a matrix direct product of L and L^* :

$$\lambda = L \otimes L^* \quad (3)$$

¹We assume that the overall phase and attenuation parameters of the Jones matrix are zero in order to make the matrix in the exponent traceless.

In general, λ is a complex matrix and it corresponds to the Lorentz transformation matrix, Λ , or, in polarization optics, it corresponds to the non-singular, nondepolarizing Mueller matrix, M . In order to have the familiar real matrix form of λ it is enough to change the basis:

$$\Lambda = A(L \otimes L^*)A^{-1} \quad (4)$$

$$A = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & i & -i & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad A^{-1} = A^\dagger = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & -i & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & i & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Now, it is straightforward to show that $SO(3,1)$ can be written as a commutative product of $SL(4, C)$ and $SL(4, C)^*$ by simply rewriting Eq.(4) in the following factorized form:

$$\Lambda = [A(L \otimes I)A^{-1}][A(I \otimes L^*)A^{-1}] = ZZ^* = Z^*Z, \quad (6)$$

$$Z = A(L \otimes I)A^{-1}, \quad Z^* = A(I \otimes L^*)A^{-1}. \quad (7)$$

Z and Z^* are the 4×4 versions of Eq.(2) expressed in terms of Σ_i matrices:

$$Z = \exp(-\frac{i}{2}\vec{\pi} \cdot \vec{\Sigma}), \quad Z^* = \exp(\frac{i}{2}\vec{\pi}^* \cdot \vec{\Sigma}^*). \quad (8)$$

$\vec{\Sigma} = (\Sigma_1, \Sigma_2, \Sigma_3)$:

$$\Sigma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Sigma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & i \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -i & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Sigma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -i & 0 \\ 0 & i & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

These are traceless Hermitian matrices and they satisfy the same commutation relations as σ_i matrices

$$\left[\frac{1}{2}\Sigma_i, \frac{1}{2}\Sigma_j \right] = \frac{i}{2}\epsilon^{ijk}\Sigma_k. \quad (10)$$

By definition, $\Sigma_\mu = A(\sigma_\mu \otimes I)A^{-1}$, ($\mu = 0, 1, 2, 3$), Σ_0 is the 4×4 identity. Σ_μ basis do not form a complete set for 4×4 matrices, but the set of $\Sigma_\mu \Sigma_\nu^*$ does.

We also define the spinor metric g for $SL(4, C)$ that corresponds to the spinor metric ϵ of $SL(2, C)$:

$$g = g^{\mu\nu} = i\eta\Sigma_2^* = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ -i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}; \quad g^{-1} = g_{\mu\nu} = g^\dagger. \quad (11)$$

η is the mostly minus Minkowski metric².

Z matrix satisfies the relation $Z^T g Z = g$, because of the property, $g^{-1} Z^T g = Z^{-1}$ and it can be shown that

$$g\Sigma_i g^{-1} = -\Sigma_i^* \quad (12)$$

²We can define the spinor metric for $SL(4, C)$ as $i\eta\Sigma_1^*$ or $i\eta\Sigma_3^*$ if we like. These metrics also have the same properties of g .

Now, we address the following question: Which object is transformed by the Z matrix? In order to answer this question we will first establish a connection between the spinor formalism of the Lorentz group and Z matrices, then we will show that generalized eigenvectors of Σ_i^* and Σ_i matrices can be interpreted as 4-component covariant and contravariant spinors that are transformed by Z and \hat{Z} matrices, respectively.

0.2 Coherency matrix, quaternion forms and their transformation properties

Let ω be a 2-component ordinary complex vector and L be an element of $SL(2, C)$. As an example, L can be the Jones matrix of polarization optics and ω can be the Jones vector representing a plane wave of a completely polarized light. L acts on ω :

$$\omega \rightarrow \omega' = L\omega \quad (13)$$

We also define the coherency matrix $\omega\omega^\dagger$ for the complete polarization state of light which is transformed as

$$\omega\omega^\dagger \rightarrow (\omega\omega^\dagger)' = (L\omega)(L\omega)^\dagger = L(\omega\omega^\dagger)L^\dagger \quad (14)$$

In terms of the components of ω

$$\omega = \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \end{pmatrix}; \quad \omega\omega^\dagger = \begin{pmatrix} uu^* & uv^* \\ vu^* & vv^* \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow (\omega\omega^\dagger)' = \begin{pmatrix} (uu^*)' & (uv^*)' \\ (vu^*)' & (vv^*)' \end{pmatrix} \quad (15)$$

We write the elements of $(\omega\omega^\dagger)'$ explicitly for further reference in terms of the elements of L :

$$(uu^*)' = L_{11}L_{11}^*uu^* + L_{11}L_{12}^*uv^* + L_{12}L_{11}^*vu^* + L_{12}L_{12}^*vv^* \quad (16)$$

$$(uv^*)' = L_{11}L_{21}^*uu^* + L_{11}L_{22}^*uv^* + L_{12}L_{21}^*vu^* + L_{12}L_{22}^*vv^* \quad (17)$$

$$(vu^*)' = L_{21}L_{11}^*uu^* + L_{21}L_{12}^*uv^* + L_{22}L_{11}^*vu^* + L_{22}L_{12}^*vv^* \quad (18)$$

$$(vv^*)' = L_{21}L_{21}^*uu^* + L_{21}L_{22}^*uv^* + L_{22}L_{21}^*vu^* + L_{22}L_{22}^*vv^* \quad (19)$$

It will be useful to write Eqs. (16 -19) in the following factorized forms:

$$(uu^*)' = UU^*, \quad (uv^*)' = UV^*, \quad (vu^*)' = VU^*, \quad (vv^*)' = VV^*, \quad (20)$$

where $U = L_{11}u + L_{12}v$, $V = L_{21}u + L_{22}v$.

We can associate $\omega\omega^\dagger$ with a 4-component real vector \vec{q} with components t, x, y, z through the substitutions, $uu^* \rightarrow t + z$, $uv^* \rightarrow x - iy$, $vu^* \rightarrow x + iy$, $vv^* \rightarrow t - z$:

$$\omega\omega^\dagger \rightarrow X = \begin{pmatrix} t + z & x - iy \\ x + iy & t - z \end{pmatrix} = tI + \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\sigma}; \quad \vec{x} = (x, y, z) \quad (21)$$

In polarization optics \vec{q} corresponds to the Stokes vector ³ and for the complete polarization state of light $\det(X) = t^2 - x^2 - y^2 - z^2 = 0$. X can also be considered as a matrix representation of a quaternion, because $-i\sigma_1, -i\sigma_2, -i\sigma_3$ matrices have the same properties as the Hamilton's quaternion basis, $\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k}$:

$$X = tI + ix(-i\sigma_1) + iy(-i\sigma_2) + iz(-i\sigma_3) = t\mathbf{1} + xi\mathbf{i} + yj\mathbf{j} + zk\mathbf{k}. \quad (22)$$

³ $s_0 = t, s_1 = z, s_2 = x, s_3 = y$.

0.3 Generalized 4-component eigenvectors and transformation properties of 2-column objects

We define four linearly independent generalized eigenvectors of Σ_3 :

$$W^{(1)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} v \\ -u \\ -iu \\ v \end{pmatrix}, \quad W^{(2)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ -v \\ iv \\ -u \end{pmatrix}, \quad W^{(3)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ iv \\ u \end{pmatrix}, \quad W^{(4)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} v \\ u \\ -iu \\ -v \end{pmatrix} \quad (23)$$

Indices in the parentheses are just labels. $W^{(1)}$ and $W^{(3)}$ correspond to $+1$ eigenvalue, $W^{(2)}$ and $W^{(4)}$ correspond to -1 eigenvalue⁴. If we set $u = v = 1/\sqrt{2}$, $W^{(a)\dagger}W^{(b)} = \delta^{ab}$ and $W^{(a)}$ vectors form a complete set of orthonormal basis for the 4-dimensional vector space.

Similarly, we also have the generalized eigenvectors of Σ_3^* :

$$W_{(1)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ -iv \\ u \end{pmatrix}, \quad W_{(2)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -v \\ -u \\ -iu \\ v \end{pmatrix}, \quad W_{(3)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -v \\ u \\ -iu \\ -v \end{pmatrix}, \quad W_{(4)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ -v \\ -iv \\ -u \end{pmatrix} \quad (24)$$

Note that, $W_{(a)}$ and $W^{(a)}$ can be converted to each other by the spinor metric of $SL(4, C)$: $W^{(a)} = gW_{(a)}$. Hence, we can interpret the eigenvectors of Σ_3 and Σ_3^* as 4-component undotted contravariant and covariant spinors, but in this section we will continue to treat them as ordinary 4-component vectors and investigate their properties by constructing the following two column objects:

$$W^{(12)} = [W^{(1)}, W^{(2)}] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} v & u \\ -u & -v \\ -iu & iv \\ v & -u \end{pmatrix}, \quad W^{(34)} = [W^{(3)}, W^{(4)}] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} u & v \\ v & u \\ iv & -iu \\ u & -v \end{pmatrix}, \quad (25)$$

$$W_{(12)} = [W_{(1)}, W_{(2)}] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} u & -v \\ v & -u \\ -iv & -iu \\ u & v \end{pmatrix}, \quad W_{(34)} = [W_{(3)}, W_{(4)}] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -v & u \\ u & -v \\ -iu & -iv \\ -v & -u \end{pmatrix} \quad (26)$$

Now consider the coherency matrix $Q_{(12)} = W_{(12)}W_{(12)}^\dagger$, which is the 4×4 version of $\omega\omega^\dagger$:

$$Q_{(12)} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} uu^* + vv^* & uv^* + vu^* & iuv^* - ivu^* & uu^* - vv^* \\ uv^* + vu^* & uu^* + vv^* & -iuu^* + ivv^* & -uv^* + vu^* \\ iuv^* - ivu^* & iuu^* - ivv^* & uu^* + vv^* & -iuv^* - ivu^* \\ uu^* - vv^* & uv^* - vu^* & iuv^* + ivu^* & uu^* + vv^* \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} t & x & y & z \\ x & t & -iz & iy \\ y & iz & t & -ix \\ z & -iy & ix & t \end{pmatrix} \quad (27)$$

Or, in terms of X :

$$Q_{(12)} = A(X \otimes I)A^{-1} \quad (28)$$

⁴We may use the generalized eigenvectors of Σ_1 or Σ_2 matrices as well, but, in that case, we have to employ the other forms of the spinor metric.

Since, $-i\Sigma_i$ matrices also have the same properties as the Hamilton's basis quaternions, $Q_{(12)}$ is a quaternion of the first kind based on Σ_μ matrices with signature (t, x, y, z) :

$$Q_{(12)} = t\Sigma_0 + \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\Sigma} \quad (29)$$

Similarly, $Q_{(34)} = W_{(34)}W_{(34)}^\dagger$ is also a quaternion of the first kind with signature $(t, -x, y, -z)$. On the other hand, $\tilde{Q}^{(12)} = W^{(12)}W^{(12)\dagger}$ has a different form:

$$\tilde{Q}^{(12)} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} uu^* + vv^* & -uv^* - vu^* & -iuv^* + ivu^* & -uu^* + vv^* \\ -uv^* - vu^* & uu^* + vv^* & -iuv^* + ivu^* & -uv^* + vu^* \\ -iuv^* + ivu^* & iuv^* - ivu^* & uu^* + vv^* & -iuv^* - ivu^* \\ -uu^* + vv^* & uv^* - vu^* & iuv^* + ivu^* & uu^* + vv^* \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} t & -x & -y & -z \\ -x & t & -iz & iy \\ -y & iz & t & -ix \\ -z & -iy & ix & t \end{pmatrix} \quad (30)$$

$\tilde{Q}^{(12)}$ has signature $(t, -x, -y, -z)$, but it is a quaternion of the second kind based on Σ_μ^* matrices:

$$\tilde{Q}^{(12)} = t\Sigma_0 - \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\Sigma}^* \quad (31)$$

Also, $\tilde{Q}^{(34)} = W^{(34)}W^{(34)\dagger}$ is a quaternion of the second kind with signature $(t, x, -y, z)$. It can be easily seen that

$$\tilde{Q}^{(12)} = \eta Q_{(12)} \eta = g Q_{(12)} g^{-1} \quad (32)$$

$$\tilde{Q}^{(34)} = \eta Q_{(34)} \eta = g Q_{(34)} g^{-1} \quad (33)$$

We already know how these kind of objects transform: they transform as quaternions. If Q is a quaternion of the first kind it transforms as $Q \rightarrow S' = ZQZ^\dagger$. Then, if \tilde{Q} is a quaternion of the second kind, using the relations $\tilde{Q} = Q^T$ and $\tilde{Z} = Z^T$, it can be shown that \tilde{Q} transforms as $\tilde{Q} \rightarrow \tilde{Q}' = \tilde{Z}^\dagger \tilde{Q} \tilde{Z}$.

If \vec{q} is a Stokes vector which is transformed by the Mueller matrix, $\vec{q} \rightarrow \vec{q}' = M\vec{q}$, and if Q and \tilde{Q} correspond to the same \vec{q} , then Q' and \tilde{Q}' correspond to the same \vec{q}' . There are also combinations like $W_{(ab)}W^{(ab)\dagger}$, but these are not quaternions of any kind, they correspond to spinorial objects that we will discuss in Sec. 0.6 and we will show that they transform as mixed spinor pairs under $SL(4, C)$.

0.4 $(\frac{1}{2}, 0)$ and $(0, \frac{1}{2})$ representations of 2-component and 4-component spinors

In the previous sections we have studied 2-component and 4-component vectors, associated quaternion forms and their transformation properties. In this section we will make a transition to 2-component and 4-component spinors.

Let $L = \exp(-\frac{i}{2}\vec{\pi} \cdot \vec{\sigma})$ be the $(\frac{1}{2}, 0)$ representation of the Lorentz group that acts on the 2-component left-chiral spinor ξ_L :

$$\xi_L \rightarrow \xi'_L = L\xi_L. \quad (34)$$

Let $\dot{L} = \exp(-\frac{i}{2}\vec{\pi}^* \cdot \vec{\sigma})$ be the dotted version corresponding to the $(0, \frac{1}{2})$ representation of the Lorentz group. $\dot{L} = (L^{-1})^\dagger = \epsilon^{-1}L^*\epsilon$ because of the relation

$$\epsilon^{-1}\sigma_i^*\epsilon = -\sigma_i; \quad \epsilon = \epsilon^{ab} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \epsilon^{-1} = \epsilon_{ab} = \epsilon^\dagger. \quad (35)$$

\dot{L} acts on the 2-component right-chiral spinor ξ_R :

$$\xi_R \rightarrow \xi'_R = \dot{L}\xi_R \quad (36)$$

where $\xi_R = \epsilon\xi_L^*$.

Similar relations hold for $SL(4, C)$. Let $Z = \exp(-\frac{i}{2}\vec{\pi} \cdot \vec{\Sigma})$ be the $(\frac{1}{2}, 0)$ representation of $SL(4, C)$ that acts on the 4-component left-chiral spinors $\chi_{(a)}$:

$$\chi_{(a)} \rightarrow \chi'_{(a)} = Z\chi_{(a)}, \quad (37)$$

where $\chi_{(a)}$ ($a = 1, 2, 3, 4$) are the generalized eigenvectors of Σ_3^* that we have introduced in the previous section, but now regarded as 4-component undotted covariant spinors:

$$W_{(1)} \rightarrow \chi_{(1)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ -iv \\ u \end{pmatrix}, \quad W_{(2)} \rightarrow \chi_{(2)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -v \\ -u \\ -iu \\ v \end{pmatrix} \quad (38)$$

$$W_{(3)} \rightarrow \chi_{(3)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -v \\ u \\ -iu \\ -v \end{pmatrix}, \quad W_{(4)} \rightarrow \chi_{(4)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ -v \\ -iv \\ -u \end{pmatrix} \quad (39)$$

Indices in the parentheses are still simply labels for 4-component spinors.

Similarly, $\dot{Z} = \exp(-\frac{i}{2}\vec{\pi}^* \cdot \vec{\Sigma})$ is the $(0, \frac{1}{2})$ representation. $\dot{Z} = (Z^{-1})^\dagger = g^{-1}Z^*g$ due to the relation $g^{-1}\Sigma_i^*g = -\Sigma_i$. We define the generalized eigenvectors of Σ_3 as the 4-component undotted contravariant spinors for this representation:

$$W^{(1)} \rightarrow \chi^{(1)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} v \\ -u \\ -iu \\ v \end{pmatrix}, \quad W^{(2)} \rightarrow \chi^{(2)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ -v \\ iv \\ -u \end{pmatrix} \quad (40)$$

$$W^{(3)} \rightarrow \chi^{(3)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ iv \\ u \end{pmatrix}, \quad W^{(4)} \rightarrow \chi^{(4)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} v \\ u \\ -iu \\ -v \end{pmatrix} \quad (41)$$

Undotted 4-component contravariant spinors are related to undotted 4-component covariant spinors by the $SL(4, C)$ metric, $\chi^{(a)} = g\chi_{(a)}$, and their dotted versions are defined as

$$\dot{\chi}^{(a)} = (g\chi_{(a)})^*, \quad g = i\eta\Sigma_2^* \quad (42)$$

\dot{Z} acts on $\dot{\chi}^{(a)}$ and $\dot{\chi}^{(a)} \rightarrow \dot{\chi}^{(a)'} = \dot{Z}\dot{\chi}^{(a)}$:

$$\dot{\chi}^{(a)} \rightarrow \dot{\chi}^{(a)'} = (gZ\chi_{(a)})^* = g^*Z^*\dot{\chi}_{(a)} = [g^*Z^*(g^*)^{-1}][g^*\dot{\chi}_{(a)}] = [g^{-1}Z^*g]\dot{\chi}^{(a)} = \dot{Z}\dot{\chi}^{(a)}. \quad (43)$$

In an analogy with the 2-component spinors, scalar product of 4-component spinors is defined in the usual way

$$\tilde{\psi}^T \chi \quad (44)$$

here \sim indicates that $\tilde{\psi}$ is an undotted contravariant spinor. It is straightforward to show that the scalar product is preserved under the $SL(4, C)$ transformation:

$$\tilde{\psi}^T \chi \rightarrow (\tilde{\psi}^T \chi)' = ((Z^{-1})^T \tilde{\psi})^T Z \chi = \tilde{\psi}^T \chi \quad (45)$$

0.5 $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$ representation, 2-component spinors and 4-vectors

Let x^μ be a 4-vector of the Minkowski space. In the $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$ representation, two copies of $SL(2, C)$ act on the Hermitian matrix $X = x^\mu \sigma_\mu$:

$$X \rightarrow X' = L X L^\dagger \quad (46)$$

This transformation property of X is similar to the transformation of a second rank spinor with one index undotted and the other index dotted:

$$(X')^{\mu\nu} = L^\mu_\delta (L^*)^{\dot{\nu}}_{\dot{\rho}} X^{\delta\rho}; \quad \mu, \nu, \delta, \rho = 0, 1, 2, 3. \quad (47)$$

Eq. (47) is equivalent to the transformation by the 4×4 real Lorentz matrix, Λ :

$$x^\mu \rightarrow x'^\mu = \Lambda^\mu_\nu x^\nu \quad (48)$$

But, in this section we want to give a more direct relation between 2-component spinors and 4-vectors by reformulating Eq. 14 in terms of ξ_L and ξ_R :

$$\omega \omega^\dagger \rightarrow \xi_L \xi_R^T = \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \end{pmatrix} (\dot{v}, -\dot{u}) = \begin{pmatrix} u\dot{v} & -u\dot{u} \\ v\dot{v} & -v\dot{u} \end{pmatrix} \quad (49)$$

Here we write ξ_R in terms of the components u and v of ξ_L . According to the transformation properties of left and right spinors

$$\xi_L \xi_R^T \rightarrow L \xi_L (\dot{L} \xi_R)^T = L (\xi_L \xi_R^T) \dot{L}^T. \quad (50)$$

We calculate the resultant matrix explicitly by using $\dot{L} = (L^{-1})^\dagger = \begin{pmatrix} L_{22}^* & -L_{21}^* \\ -L_{12}^* & L_{11}^* \end{pmatrix}$:

$$\begin{pmatrix} u\dot{v} & -u\dot{u} \\ v\dot{v} & -v\dot{u} \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} (u\dot{v})' & (-u\dot{u})' \\ (v\dot{v})' & (-v\dot{u})' \end{pmatrix} \quad (51)$$

where

$$(u\dot{v})' = L_{11} L_{21}^* u\dot{u} + L_{11} L_{22}^* u\dot{v} + L_{12} L_{21}^* v\dot{u} + L_{12} L_{22}^* v\dot{v} \quad (52)$$

$$(u\dot{u})' = L_{11} L_{11}^* u\dot{u} + L_{11} L_{12}^* u\dot{v} + L_{12} L_{11}^* v\dot{u} + L_{12} L_{12}^* v\dot{v} \quad (53)$$

$$(v\dot{v})' = L_{21} L_{21}^* u\dot{u} + L_{21} L_{22}^* u\dot{v} + L_{22} L_{21}^* v\dot{u} + L_{22} L_{22}^* v\dot{v} \quad (54)$$

$$(v\dot{u})' = L_{21} L_{11}^* u\dot{u} + L_{21} L_{12}^* u\dot{v} + L_{22} L_{11}^* v\dot{u} + L_{22} L_{12}^* v\dot{v} \quad (55)$$

These equations are the same as Eqs. (16 -19), hence Eq.(50) is the spinor version of the transformation, $X \rightarrow L X L^\dagger$.

0.6 Pairs of 4-component spinors and 4-vectors

In this section we interpret $W_{(ab)}$ and $W^{(ab)}$ that we have defined in Section 0.3 as undotted covariant and undotted contravariant 4-component spinor pairs $\chi_{(ab)}$ and $\chi^{(ab)}$, respectively:

$$W_{(12)} \rightarrow \chi_{(12)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} u & -v \\ v & -u \\ -iv & -iu \\ u & v \end{pmatrix}, \quad W_{(34)} \rightarrow \chi_{(34)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -v & u \\ u & -v \\ -iu & -iv \\ -v & -u \end{pmatrix}, \quad (56)$$

$$W^{(12)} \rightarrow \chi^{(12)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} v & u \\ -u & -v \\ -iu & iv \\ v & -u \end{pmatrix}, \quad W^{(34)} \rightarrow \chi^{(34)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} u & v \\ v & u \\ iv & -iu \\ u & -v \end{pmatrix}, \quad (57)$$

We consider the spinorial object $S = \chi_{(12)}(\chi^{(12)})^\dagger = \chi_{(12)}\dot{\chi}^{(12)T}$, which is the 4-component analogue of $\xi_L\xi_R^T$ that we have studied in Section 0.5. As we have noted previously, this object is not in the quaternion form. It transforms as a mixed spinor:

$$S \rightarrow S' = Z\chi_{(12)}(\dot{Z}\dot{\chi}^{(12)})^T = ZS\dot{Z}^T. \quad (58)$$

This is the $SL(4, C)$ version of Eq.(50). In order to write the result explicitly we express Z and \dot{Z} in terms of the elements of L :

$$Z = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} L_{11} + L_{22} & L_{12} + L_{21} & iL_{12} - iL_{21} & L_{11} - L_{22} \\ L_{12} + L_{21} & L_{11} + L_{22} & -iL_{11} + iL_{22} & -L_{12} + L_{21} \\ iL_{12} - iL_{21} & iL_{11} - iL_{22} & L_{11} + L_{22} & -iL_{12} - iL_{21} \\ L_{11} - L_{22} & L_{12} - L_{21} & iL_{12} + iL_{21} & L_{11} + L_{22} \end{pmatrix} \quad (59)$$

By letting $\tau = \frac{1}{2}(L_{11} + L_{22})$, $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}(L_{12} + L_{21})$, $\beta = \frac{i}{2}(L_{12} - L_{21})$, $\gamma = \frac{1}{2}(L_{11} - L_{22})$

$$Z = \begin{pmatrix} \tau & \alpha & \beta & \gamma \\ \alpha & \tau & -i\gamma & i\beta \\ \beta & i\gamma & \tau & -i\alpha \\ \gamma & -i\beta & i\alpha & \tau \end{pmatrix} = \tau\Sigma_0 + \alpha\Sigma_1 + \beta\Sigma_2 + \gamma\Sigma_3 \quad (60)$$

$$\dot{Z} = (Z^{-1})^\dagger = \begin{pmatrix} \tau^* & -\alpha^* & -\beta^* & -\gamma^* \\ -\alpha^* & \tau^* & i\gamma^* & -i\beta^* \\ -\beta^* & -i\gamma^* & \tau & i\alpha^* \\ \gamma^* & i\beta^* & -i\alpha^* & \tau \end{pmatrix} = \tau^*\Sigma_0 - \alpha^*\Sigma_1 - \beta^*\Sigma_2 - \gamma^*\Sigma_3 \quad (61)$$

Now, it is straightforward to show that

$$Z\chi_{(12)} = \frac{Z}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} u & -v \\ v & -u \\ -iv & -iu \\ u & v \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} U & -V \\ V & -U \\ -iV & -iU \\ U & V \end{pmatrix} \quad (62)$$

$$\dot{Z}\dot{\chi}^{(12)} = \frac{\dot{Z}}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \dot{v} & \dot{u} \\ -\dot{u} & -\dot{v} \\ i\dot{u} & -i\dot{v} \\ \dot{v} & -\dot{u} \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \dot{V} & \dot{U} \\ -\dot{U} & -\dot{V} \\ i\dot{U} & -i\dot{V} \\ \dot{V} & -\dot{U} \end{pmatrix} \quad (63)$$

In short, $u \rightarrow U$ and $v \rightarrow V$, where $U = L_{11}u + L_{12}v$ and $V = L_{21}u + L_{22}v$. Accordingly, S transforms as $\omega\omega^\dagger$ and X due the Eqs.(16 -19) and the factorized forms given in Eq.(20):

$$UU^* \doteq U\dot{U}, \quad UV^* \doteq U\dot{V}, \quad VU^* \doteq V\dot{U}, \quad VV^* \doteq V\dot{V}. \quad (64)$$

As a result, $S \rightarrow S' = ZS\dot{Z}^T$ is equivalent to $X \rightarrow X' = LXL^\dagger$, hence S can be associated with the Minkowski 4-vector. Similar considerations also apply to the combination $\chi_{(34)}\chi^{(34)\dagger}$. But, in this case, the the associated 4-vector corresponds to $\epsilon X\epsilon^{-1}$.

References

- [1] D. Han, Y.S. Kim, Marilyn E. Noz, "Polarization optics and bilinear representation of the Lorentz group." Physics Letters A 219 (1996) 26-32.
- [2] K. N. Srinivasa Rao, Linear Algebra and Group Theory for Physicists, Second Edition, Hindustan Book Agency, New Delhi, India.
- [3] Sudha and A.V.Gopala Rao, "Polarization Elements: A Group Theoretical Study".
- [4] D. Han, Y. S. Kim, Marilyn E. Noz, "Jones-matrix Formalism as a Representation of the Lorentz Group," arXiv:physics/9703032V1[physics.optics] 28 Mar 1997.
- [5] E. Kuntman, M. A. Kuntman, and O. Arteaga, "Vector and matrix states for Mueller matrices of nondepolarizing optical media," J. Opt. Soc. Am. A 34, 80-86 (2017)
- [6] E. Kuntman, M. A. Kuntman, A. Canillas, and O. Arteaga, "Quaternion algebra for Stokes–Mueller formalism," J. Opt. Soc. Am. A 36, 492-497 (2019)
- [7] R. M. A. Azzam, "Propagation of partially polarized light through anisotropic media with or without depolarization: A differential 4×4 matrix calculus," J. Opt. Soc. Am. 68, 1756 (1978).
- [8] R. Barakat, "Exponential versions of the Jones and Mueller–Jones polarization matrices," J. Opt. Soc. Am. A/Vol. 13, No. 1 (1996).
- [9] S.R. Cloude, "Group theory and polarization algebra", Optik 75, 26-36 (1986).
- [10] W. R. Hamilton, "On a new species of imaginary quantities connected with the theory of quaternions," Proceedings of the Royal Irish Academy, 2:424–434 (1844).
- [11] Bařkal, Sibel and Kim, Young S and Noz, Marilyn E, "Physics of the Lorentz Group," Morgan and Claypool Publishers (2015).
- [12] A.A. Bogush, V.M. Red'kov, "On unique parametrization of the linear group $GL(4,C)$ and its subgroups by using the Dirac matrix algebra basis," arXiv:hep-th/0607054V1 (2006).